

Digital Innovations for Clinical Decision-Making in the Prevention and Treatment of Urinary Tract Infections in Menopausal Women: A Systematic Review

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Table 1: Contributions of Author

1 Background

Menopause is characterized by the permanent cessation of ovarian function and a progressive decline in sex steroids (Davis et al., 2015; Schoenaker et al., 2014). These hormonal changes contribute to the Genitourinary Syndrome of Menopause (GSM), which includes urinary symptoms and recurrent urinary tract infections (UTIs) (Monteleone et al., 2018; Jung et al., 2019). Approximately 50% of postmenopausal women experience GSM (Phillips et al., 2021), and recurrent UTIs represent a major clinical concern due to repeated antibiotic exposure and the growing risk of antimicrobial resistance (Sanyaolu et al., 2023).

Common uropathogens in menopausal women include Enterobacterales such as *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, including Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL)-producing strains (Priyanka et al., 2020; Ahn et al., 2023). The World Health Organization (WHO) has classified ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae as critical-priority pathogens due to their global spread and associated mortality (WHO, 2024). The increasing use of antibiotics further exacerbates antimicrobial resistance and complicates clinical management (Ali et al., 2021).

Preventive and management strategies include non-antibiotic therapies (Caretto et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2018; Park et al., 2023; Abdullatif et al., 2021), antimicrobial stewardship programs, and multidisciplinary care approaches (Kranz et al., 2024; Ackerman et al., 2026; Zahn et al., 2024). These approaches are supported by major international guidelines, including those from the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE, 2024), the European Association of Urology (EAU, Kranz et al., 2024), the European Menopause and Andropause Society (EMAS, 2024), the Australasian Menopause Society (AMS, 2024), the American Urological Association in collaboration with the Canadian Urological Association and the Society of Urodynamics Female Pelvic Medicine & Urogenital Reconstruction (AUA/CUA/SUFU, 2025, Ackerman et al., 2026), as well as the North American Menopause Society (NAMS, 2022; 2020). While these guidelines establish evidence-based standards for infection prevention and antimicrobial stewardship, they offer limited specific recommendations regarding the integration of digital health technologies in the prevention and management of UTIs in menopausal women.

In parallel, the incorporation of digital tools, such as health monitoring applications (Mazaheri Habibi et al., 2024), wearable devices (Zhang et al., 2023), cloud-based platforms (Rea et al., 2018), smartphone technologies (Zagorovsky et al., 2022), nanotechnology approaches (Qindeel et al., 2021), machine learning systems (Capstick et al., 2024), artificial neural network models (Naik et al., 2024), and artificial intelligence technologies (Elbehiry et al., 2022), can further enhance preventive strategies and optimize patient care.

However, evidence remains fragmented regarding which digital technologies have been specifically developed for menopausal women with UTIs, the clinical effectiveness of these technologies, their impact on quality of care and antimicrobial stewardship, and the modalities of implementation across different menopausal stages (Panjwani et al., 2025).

Therefore, the overall objective of this systematic review is to identify, evaluate, and synthesize the evidence on digital health technologies designed to support the prevention and management of urinary tract infections in menopausal women. The review will assess the clinical effectiveness, implementation characteristics, and stage-specific applicability of these technologies in order to inform clinical practice, health policy, and future research.

2 Review Questions

2.1 Main Review Question

"How do digital health technologies support clinical decision-making in the prevention and management of urinary tract infections (UTIs) in women across all stages of menopause?"

2.2 Secondary Review Questions

- **What types of digital health technologies** (e.g., clinical decision support systems, telemedicine platforms, mobile applications, AI-based tools) are currently used to support the prevention and treatment of UTIs in menopausal women?
- **How effective are these digital technologies** in improving clinical outcomes, prevention strategies, and treatment appropriateness for UTIs in menopausal women?
- **To what extent do digital tools enhance quality of care, antibiotic stewardship, and adherence to clinical guidelines** in the management of UTIs during the menopausal transition and postmenopause?
- **How do digital innovations support healthcare professionals in evidence-based decision-making** across different menopausal stages?
- **What are the barriers and facilitators** to implementing digital health technologies for UTI management in menopausal women?
- **What is the impact of digital technologies on patient-reported outcomes**, including satisfaction, engagement, and adherence to preventive measures?

3 Methods

We will conduct the systematic review following the guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021). We will obtain data from scientific publications (papers).

3.1 Overview (PICO Summary)

The table below summarises the review scope. Full eligibility criteria are in Section 2; outcomes are detailed in Section 4.

Component	Details
Population	Women in perimenopause, menopause, or postmenopause (≥ 40 years with menopausal symptoms; ≥ 45 years with/at risk of UTIs even without explicit menopausal staging). Healthcare professionals managing UTIs in this population.
Intervention	Digital health technologies for UTI prevention/management: CDSS, telemedicine platforms, mobile apps, AI/ML tools, chatbots, wearables, web portals, remote monitoring, e-prescribing systems.
Comparator	Standard care without digital support; alternative digital tools; pre-implementation data. No comparator required for observational/descriptive studies.
Outcomes	Primary: UTI incidence, recurrence rate, time to diagnosis/treatment, healthcare utilisation, re-hospitalisation, mortality. Secondary: antibiotic stewardship, guideline adherence, patient satisfaction, QoL, cost-effectiveness, technology usability.

3.2. Eligibility Criteria

3.2.1 Inclusion Criteria

Population

- Women in any stage of menopause:
 - Perimenopause: menstrual irregularities + age ≥ 40 years
 - Menopause: amenorrhea ≥ 12 consecutive months
 - Postmenopause: any time after menopause (early < 5 years; late ≥ 5 years)
- Women aged ≥ 45 years with/at risk of UTIs, even when menopausal status is not explicitly reported
- Women aged ≥ 40 years with documented menopausal symptoms or GSM, regardless of explicit menopausal staging
- Healthcare professionals managing UTIs in menopausal women

Intervention

Any digital health technology supporting UTI prevention and/or management, including:

- Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS), standalone or EHR-integrated
- Alert systems for diagnosis, treatment, or antibiotic selection
- Telemedicine and remote consultation platforms
- Mobile applications (patient-facing or clinician-facing)
- AI/ML tools for risk prediction, diagnosis, or treatment optimisation
- Chatbots and automated triage systems
- Wearable devices and biosensors for physiological monitoring
- Web-based patient portals and education platforms
- Electronic prescribing systems with decision support

Study Designs

- RCTs and quasi-experimental studies
- Observational cohort studies (prospective and retrospective)
- Case-control and cross-sectional studies
- Before-after (pre-post) studies
- Pilot, feasibility, and implementation studies

Other Eligibility Parameters

- Publication period: January 2000 – February 2026
- Languages: no restrictions (non-English studies translated by professional services if selected)
- Settings: community, primary care, hospital (inpatient/outpatient), specialty clinics, long-term care, home care with remote monitoring
- Geography: no limitations

3.2.2 Exclusion Criteria**Population**

- Studies exclusively on pre-menopausal women (age <40 years without menopausal status)
- Studies with mean age <45 years and no menopausal stratification
- Studies exclusively on men
- Studies on premature ovarian insufficiency (POI) as the primary condition, unless menopausal women are also included

Condition

- Infections other than UTIs (STIs, vaginal infections without UTI component)
- Studies exclusively on asymptomatic bacteriuria without clinical UTI outcomes

Intervention

- Non-digital interventions only (pharmacological, surgical, no digital component)
- General telemedicine platforms not specifically addressing UTI prevention or management

Publication Type

- Case reports and case series (n < 10)
- Editorials, letters, commentaries without original data
- Conference abstracts with insufficient data (authors will be contacted for full data)
- Systematic reviews and meta-analyses (used for citation searching only)
- Guidelines and consensus statements (used as reference only)
- Protocols without results

Quality

- Studies with insufficient methodological detail to assess validity

- Studies with high risk of bias across multiple domains (determined after quality assessment)

3.3 Search Strategy

3.3.1 Databases

- **PubMed/MEDLINE** (National Library of Medicine)
- **Scopus** (Elsevier)
- **Web of Science Core Collection** (Clarivate Analytics)
- **Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL)**

3.3.2 Search Structure

All databases are searched using three Boolean concept blocks:

- Block 1 (Population): menopause-related terms, age qualifiers, GSM
- Block 2 (Condition): UTI terms (cystitis, pyelonephritis, CAUTI, recurrent UTI, GSM)
- Block 3 (Intervention): digital health terms (CDSS, AI, telemedicine, mHealth, EHR, chatbots, wearables, e-prescribing)

3.3.3 Database-Specific Search Strings

Database	Search String (summary)
PubMed/MEDLINE (National Library of Medicine)	("Women"[MeSH] OR women OR woman OR female* OR menopaus* OR postmenopaus* OR perimenopaus*) AND ("Urinary Tract Infections"[MeSH] OR "urinary tract infection*" OR UTI OR cystitis OR "recurrent urinary tract infection*" OR "recurrent UTI" OR pyelonephritis OR "catheter-associated urinary tract infection*" OR CAUTI OR "genitourinary syndrome of menopause" OR GSM) AND ("Clinical Decision Support Systems" OR "Decision Support Systems, Clinical"[MeSH] OR "Telemedicine"[MeSH] OR "Remote Consultation"[MeSH] OR "Mobile Applications"[MeSH] OR "Artificial Intelligence"[MeSH] OR AI OR "Machine Learning"[MeSH] OR "Medical Informatics"[MeSH] OR digital health OR eHealth OR mHealth OR telehealth OR telemedicine OR telemonitoring OR "remote monitoring" OR "clinical decision support" OR CDSS OR "computerized decision support" OR "electronic health record*" OR EHR OR "electronic medical record*" OR EMR OR "machine learning" OR "predictive model*" OR "risk model*" OR "risk prediction" OR algorithm* OR "electronic prescribing" OR e-prescribing OR chatbot* OR "mobile app*") Filters: Humans, from 2000 - 2026
Scopus (Elsevier)	(TITLE-ABS-KEY((women OR woman OR female OR menopause OR postmenopause OR perimenopause)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(("urinary tract infection" OR UTI OR cystitis OR "recurrent urinary tract infection" OR "recurrent UTI" OR pyelonephritis OR "catheter-associated urinary tract infection" OR CAUTI OR "genitourinary syndrome of menopause" OR GSM)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(("clinical decision support" OR "decision support systems" OR telemedicine OR "remote consultation" OR "mobile applications" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "machine learning" OR "medical informatics" OR "digital health" OR eHealth OR mHealth OR telehealth OR telemonitoring OR "remote monitoring" OR CDSS OR "computerized decision support" OR "electronic health record" OR EHR OR "electronic medical record" OR EMR OR "predictive model" OR "risk model" OR "risk prediction" OR algorithm OR "electronic prescribing" OR e-prescribing OR chatbot OR "mobile app"))) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD,"Human"))
Web of Science (Clarivate Analytics)	TS=(women OR woman OR female OR menopause OR postmenopause OR perimenopause*) AND TS=(urinary tract infection OR UTI OR cystitis OR recurrent urinary tract infection OR recurrent UTI OR pyelonephritis OR catheter-associated urinary tract infection OR CAUTI OR genitourinary syndrome of menopause OR GSM) AND TS=(clinical decision support OR decision support systems OR telemedicine OR remote consultation OR mobile applications OR artificial intelligence OR AI OR machine learning OR medical informatics OR digital health OR eHealth OR mHealth OR telehealth OR telemonitoring OR remote monitoring OR CDSS OR computerized decision support OR electronic health record* OR EHR OR electronic medical record* OR EMR OR predictive model* OR risk model* OR risk prediction OR algorithm* OR electronic prescribing OR e-prescribing OR chatbot* OR mobile app*)AND PY=(2000-2026)
Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL)	(women OR woman OR female OR menopause OR postmenopause OR perimenopause*) in Title Abstract Keyword AND (urinary tract infection OR UTI OR cystitis OR recurrent urinary tract infection OR recurrent UTI OR pyelonephritis OR catheter-associated urinary tract infection OR CAUTI OR genitourinary syndrome of menopause OR GSM) in Title Abstract Keyword AND (clinical decision support OR decision support systems OR telemedicine OR remote consultation OR mobile applications OR artificial intelligence OR AI OR machine learning OR medical informatics OR digital health OR eHealth OR mHealth OR telehealth OR telemonitoring OR remote

monitoring OR CDSS OR computerized decision support OR electronic health record* OR EHR OR electronic medical record* OR EMR OR predictive model* OR risk model* OR risk prediction OR algorithm* OR electronic prescribing OR e-prescribing OR chatbot* OR mobile app*) in Title Abstract Keyword - with Publication Year from 2000 to 2026.

3.3.4 Additional Search Methods

1. Backward citation searching reference lists of included studies and relevant reviews
2. Forward citation searching: Google Scholar and Web of Science
3. Grey literature: Google Scholar (first 200 results); EMAS, NAMS, ICS, IUGA conference proceedings
4. Clinical trial registries: ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO ICTRP, EU Clinical Trials Register
5. Expert consultation: key experts in menopause, urology, and digital health contacted for unpublished or ongoing studies
6. Industry contacts: manufacturers of relevant digital health technologies contacted for unpublished data

3.3.5 Search Documentation

Each search is documented with: date, database version/platform, exact string used, number of results retrieved, filters applied, and name of the searcher. Searches will be updated immediately before final analysis.

3.4 Outcomes

For each outcome, the following will be extracted where available: measurement instrument, timing, baseline and post-intervention values, effect size, measures of precision (95% CIs), and p-values.

Type	Outcome	Measurement
Primary	UTI incidence	New episodes per patient per year
Primary	UTI recurrence	≥2 episodes/6 months or ≥3/12 months
Primary	Time to diagnosis & treatment	Hours/days from symptom onset to diagnosis; diagnosis to treatment
Primary	Healthcare utilisation	Primary care visits, ED visits, admissions, teleconsultations, diagnostic tests
Primary	Re-hospitalisation	Number/rate of UTI-related readmissions; time to readmission
Primary	Mortality	UTI-related and all-cause mortality
Secondary	Antibiotic stewardship	Prescribing appropriateness, spectrum, duration, DDD consumption
Secondary	Guideline adherence	Compliance with NICE, EAU, EMAS, AMS, AUA-CUA-SUFU, NAMS
Secondary	Patient adherence	Hydration, hygiene, prophylaxis, non-antibiotic therapies
Secondary	HCP decision efficiency	Treatment choice changes, time to decision, diagnostic accuracy
Secondary	Patient satisfaction & QoL	Satisfaction scores, PREMs, symptom severity, quality of life

Secondary	Antimicrobial resistance	Pathogen distribution, MDR/XDR rates, ESBL/CRE/MRSA/VRE
Secondary	Cost-effectiveness	Direct costs, cost/episode prevented, cost/QALY, ROI
Secondary	Technology usability	SUS scores, acceptability, integration barriers, training needs

5. DATA EXTRACTION (SELECTION AND CODING)

5.1 Study Selection Process

5.1.1 Deduplication

Search results from all databases will be exported to a reference management system (Rayyan, free online version; Rayyan Systems Inc.). Duplicate records will be identified and removed using:

- Automatic deduplication features in Rayyan
- Manual verification of potential duplicates
- Documentation of the number of duplicates removed

Rayyan is a web-based platform designed to support systematic reviews (Ouzzani et al., 2016).

5.1.2 Title and Abstract Screening

Process:

- Two reviewers will screen all titles and abstracts independently
- A second reviewer will be consulted for uncertain cases
- Screening will be conducted using Rayyan software
- Liberal inclusion at this stage: studies will be excluded only if clearly irrelevant

Screening criteria:

- Does the study involve menopausal women or adults (potential menopausal population)?
- Does the study address urinary tract infections?
- Does the study involve any digital health technology?
- If unsure, include for full-text review

Documentation:

- Number of records screened
- Number of records excluded with reasons
- Number of records proceeding to full-text review
- Inter-rater agreement (Cohen's kappa) for subset checked by second reviewer

5.1.3 Full-Text Review

Process:

- Two independent reviewers will assess full-text articles
- Each reviewer will document reasons for exclusion using standardized form
- Disagreements will be resolved through discussion
- A third reviewer will be consulted if consensus cannot be reached
- Authors will be contacted for clarification if eligibility cannot be determined from published information

Documentation:

- Number of full-text articles assessed
- Number of articles excluded at full-text stage with specific reasons
- Number of articles included in final synthesis
- Inter-rater agreement (Cohen's kappa)

5.1.4 PRISMA Flow Diagram

A complete PRISMA 2020 flow diagram will be created documenting:

- Records identified through database searching
- Records identified through other sources
- Records after duplicates removed
- Records screened
- Records excluded with reasons
- Full-text articles assessed for eligibility
- Full-text articles excluded with reasons
- Studies included in qualitative synthesis
- Studies included in quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis)

5.2 Data Extraction

5.2.1 Data Extraction Tool

A standardized data extraction form will be developed and pilot-tested on 5-10 randomly selected included studies. The form will be refined based on pilot testing before full data extraction.

Data extraction will be performed using a structured Excel/database template.

5.2.2 Data Extraction Process

- Two independent reviewers will extract data from all included studies
- Discrepancies will be resolved through discussion or consultation with third reviewer
- Authors will be contacted for missing or unclear data
- Maximum two attempts to contact authors (initial email + one reminder after 2 weeks)

5.2.3 Data Extraction Items

SECTION A: STUDY GENERAL INFORMATION

Variable	Description/Notes
Study ID	Unique identifier assigned by reviewers
Study title	Full title of the study
Authors	Full list of authors (first author + et al. for citation)
Year of publication	Year published
Journal/Source	Name of journal or other source (conference, thesis, report)
Country/Geographic context	Country where study conducted; region if multi-country
Study design	RCT, quasi-experimental, cohort (prospective/retrospective), case-control, cross-sectional, before-after, pilot/feasibility, mixed methods, implementation study
Study setting	Community, primary care, hospital (inpatient/outpatient/ED), specialty clinic, long-term care, telemedicine, mixed
Funding source	Government, industry, academic, mixed, none, not reported
Conflicts of interest	Declared conflicts: yes/no/not reported; specify if yes
Study objective(s)	Primary and secondary objectives as stated by authors
Trial registration	Registry and number if applicable (e.g., ClinicalTrials.gov NCT#)

SECTION B: POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

Variable	Description/Notes
Sample Size	
Total sample size	Total N at baseline
Sample size by group	N per intervention/control group
Sample size at follow-up	N completing study; attrition rate (%)
Demographics	
Mean age (SD)	Years; or median (IQR) if reported
Age range	Minimum - maximum age
Age groups	N (%) in defined age categories if reported "Age Groups ≤40;40–49; 50–59; 60–69 e ≥70"
Menopause Characteristics	
Menopause stage	N (%) in: perimenopausal, menopausal, early postmenopausal (<5y), late postmenopausal (≥5y), not specified
Criteria for menopause stage	How stage was defined (e.g., amenorrhea duration, hormonal criteria, self-report)
Mean time since menopause	Years (SD) or median (IQR) for postmenopausal women
Hormone therapy use	N (%) current users, past users, never users
Ethnicity/Race	
Racial/ethnic distribution	N (%) by category as reported
Comorbidities	
Diabetes mellitus	N (%) with diabetes
Hypertension	N (%)
Obesity	N (%) or mean BMI (SD)
Renal impairment	N (%) with reduced kidney function
Immunocompromised status	N (%) (e.g., immunosuppressive drugs, HIV)
Other relevant comorbidities	Specify
Inclusion Criteria	

Inclusion criteria	As stated by authors
Exclusion Criteria	
Exclusion criteria	As stated by authors

SECTION C: UTI CHARACTERISTICS

Variable	Description/Notes
UTI Epidemiology	
Prevalence of UTI in sample	N (%) with UTI at baseline or during study
UTI incidence	Rate per person-year or per follow-up period
N° of infections by age group	Distribution if reported
N° of infections by menopause stage	Distribution if reported
History of recurrent UTI	N (%) with prior recurrent UTI (≥ 2 in 6mo or ≥ 3 in 12mo)
Type of UTI	
Type(s) of UTI included	Tick all that apply: <input type="checkbox"/> Uncomplicated cystitis <input type="checkbox"/> Complicated UTI <input type="checkbox"/> Pyelonephritis <input type="checkbox"/> Asymptomatic bacteriuria <input type="checkbox"/> Catheter-associated UTI (CAUTI) <input type="checkbox"/> Recurrent UTI <input type="checkbox"/> Urosepsis <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified
Diagnostic Criteria	
Diagnostic criteria for UTI	Clinical symptoms + urinalysis + culture? Culture threshold (e.g., $\geq 10^5$ CFU/mL)? Symptoms only?
Catheter Use	
Bladder catheter use	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not reported
Type of catheter	Indwelling, intermittent, suprapubic
Duration of catheterization	Days/weeks; mean (SD) or median (IQR)
Proportion with catheter	N (%)
Pathogens	
Pathogens isolated	N (%) for each species: <input type="checkbox"/> E. coli <input type="checkbox"/> Klebsiella spp. <input type="checkbox"/> Proteus spp. <input type="checkbox"/> Enterococcus spp. <input type="checkbox"/> Pseudomonas aeruginosa <input type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii <input type="checkbox"/> Staphylococcus spp. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed flora <input type="checkbox"/> Not reported
Antimicrobial Resistance	
Resistance testing performed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not reported
Multidrug-resistant (MDR)	N (%) of isolates that are MDR (resistant to ≥ 3 classes)
Extensively drug-resistant (XDR)	N (%) of isolates that are XDR
Specific resistance mechanisms	N (%) with: <input type="checkbox"/> ESBL (Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase) <input type="checkbox"/> CRE (Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales) <input type="checkbox"/> CRAB (Carbapenem-resistant Acinetobacter baumannii) <input type="checkbox"/> CRPA (Carbapenem-resistant P. aeruginosa) <input type="checkbox"/> MRSA (Methicillin-resistant S. aureus) <input type="checkbox"/> VRE (Vancomycin-resistant Enterococcus) <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
Symptom Severity	
Local urinary symptoms	Presence and severity: <input type="checkbox"/> Dysuria <input type="checkbox"/> Urinary frequency <input type="checkbox"/> Urgency <input type="checkbox"/> Suprapubic pain <input type="checkbox"/> Hematuria; Severity scale used: ____
Systemic symptoms	Presence: <input type="checkbox"/> Fever <input type="checkbox"/> Flank pain <input type="checkbox"/> Chills <input type="checkbox"/> Nausea/vomiting <input type="checkbox"/> General malaise

Symptom measurement tool	Standardized tool used (specify) or ad hoc assessment
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SECTION D: INTERVENTION - DIGITAL HEALTH TECHNOLOGY

Variable	Description/Notes
Technology Identification	
Name of technology	Brand/commercial name or description if unnamed
Type of Digital Technology	
Primary technology category	Select ONE primary: <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) <input type="checkbox"/> Telemedicine/teleconsultation platform <input type="checkbox"/> Mobile application (app) <input type="checkbox"/> AI-based tool (machine learning, deep learning) <input type="checkbox"/> Electronic Health Record (EHR) integrated alert <input type="checkbox"/> Remote monitoring system <input type="checkbox"/> Chatbot/automated triage <input type="checkbox"/> Wearable device <input type="checkbox"/> Web-based platform <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify): ____
Additional technology components	Select all secondary components: <input type="checkbox"/> Patient portal <input type="checkbox"/> SMS/text messaging <input type="checkbox"/> Email notifications <input type="checkbox"/> Dashboard/data visualization <input type="checkbox"/> Educational content <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ____
Technology Description	
Detailed description	Full description of how technology works, what it does, how it is accessed
Technology platform	<input type="checkbox"/> Web-based <input type="checkbox"/> Mobile app (iOS/Android) <input type="checkbox"/> Integrated into EHR <input type="checkbox"/> Standalone software <input type="checkbox"/> Hardware device <input type="checkbox"/> Multiple platforms
Intervention Aim	
Primary aim(s)	Select all that apply: <input type="checkbox"/> Prevention of UTI <input type="checkbox"/> Early detection/diagnosis of UTI <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical decision support for diagnosis <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical decision support for treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment optimization <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring/follow-up <input type="checkbox"/> Patient education <input type="checkbox"/> Antibiotic stewardship <input type="checkbox"/> Guideline adherence <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify): ____
Target Users	
Intended users	<input type="checkbox"/> Healthcare professionals only (specify: physicians, nurses, pharmacists, other) <input type="checkbox"/> Patients only <input type="checkbox"/> Both healthcare professionals and patients
Intervention Characteristics - Duration	
Total duration of intervention	Weeks or months the intervention was available/active
Follow-up period	Duration of outcome measurement after intervention start
Duration of digital tool exposure per patient	Mean/median time patients interacted with technology
Intervention Characteristics - Frequency	
Frequency of use required	Daily, weekly, as-needed, continuous (specify)
Number of uses per patient	Mean (SD) or median (IQR) uses during study
Number of alerts generated	For CDSS: total alerts, alerts per patient, alert acceptance rate (%)
Number of teleconsultations	For telemedicine: N consultations, consultations per patient
Intervention Characteristics - Intensity	
Type of decision support	<input type="checkbox"/> Real-time alerts/recommendations <input type="checkbox"/> On-demand information tool <input type="checkbox"/> Background risk assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Periodic reminders

Integration level	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully integrated into EHR workflow <input type="checkbox"/> Partially integrated <input type="checkbox"/> Standalone (separate access)
Automation level	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully automated recommendations <input type="checkbox"/> Semi-automated (human verification) <input type="checkbox"/> Manual entry required
Recommendations provided	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; If yes, describe type (diagnostic, therapeutic, preventive)
Percentage of decisions influenced	If reported: ___% of clinical decisions used technology input
Patient Involvement	
Active patient data entry required	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial; Describe:
Self-monitoring component	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; If yes, what is monitored:
Patient engagement metrics	App usage frequency, session duration, feature utilization, completion rates
Healthcare Professional Involvement	
Type(s) of professionals involved	<input type="checkbox"/> Physicians (specify specialty) <input type="checkbox"/> Nurses <input type="checkbox"/> Pharmacists <input type="checkbox"/> Physician assistants <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ___
Training provided	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; If yes: duration (hours), format (in-person, online, hybrid), content
Workflow integration	Describe how technology fits into existing clinical workflow
Time required per use	Mean/median minutes per use if reported
Prescription changes after alerts	N (%) of alerts that led to prescription modification
Clinical Decision Support Features (if applicable)	
Knowledge base	<input type="checkbox"/> Clinical guidelines (specify which) <input type="checkbox"/> Local antibiogram data <input type="checkbox"/> Evidence-based algorithms <input type="checkbox"/> Machine learning model
Type of recommendations	<input type="checkbox"/> Diagnostic suggestions <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment recommendations <input type="checkbox"/> Antibiotic selection <input type="checkbox"/> Dosing guidance <input type="checkbox"/> Duration guidance <input type="checkbox"/> Alternative therapies <input type="checkbox"/> Preventive strategies
Alert/recommendation triggers	What criteria trigger the decision support (e.g., abnormal urinalysis, symptom input)
Guideline adherence support	Which guidelines integrated: <input type="checkbox"/> NICE <input type="checkbox"/> EAU <input type="checkbox"/> EMAS <input type="checkbox"/> AMS <input type="checkbox"/> AUA-CUA-SUFU <input type="checkbox"/> NAMS <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ___ <input type="checkbox"/> None specified
AI/Machine Learning Features (if applicable)	
Type of AI/ML	<input type="checkbox"/> Supervised learning <input type="checkbox"/> Unsupervised learning <input type="checkbox"/> Reinforcement learning <input type="checkbox"/> Deep learning <input type="checkbox"/> Natural language processing <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ___
Algorithm details	Algorithm type (e.g., logistic regression, random forest, neural network)
Training dataset	Size, source, time period of training data
Validation	<input type="checkbox"/> Internal validation <input type="checkbox"/> External validation <input type="checkbox"/> Prospective validation <input type="checkbox"/> Not reported
Performance metrics	Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, AUC-ROC, F1-score (report values)
Co-interventions	
Parallel educational program	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; If yes: duration, format, content, target audience
Updated clinical guidelines during study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; If yes, specify
Antibiotic stewardship program active	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown; If yes, describe program components
Audit & feedback implemented	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; If yes: frequency, format, recipients
Other co-interventions	Specify any other interventions running concurrently

SECTION E: COMPARATOR

Variable	Description/Notes
Comparator Type	
Comparator	<input type="checkbox"/> Standard care without digital technology <input type="checkbox"/> Alternative digital technology (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Historical control (pre-intervention period) <input type="checkbox"/> Waitlist control <input type="checkbox"/> No comparator (single-arm study)
Comparator Description	
Standard care description	Detailed description of usual care provided to control group
Differences from intervention	Key differences between intervention and control conditions

SECTION F: OUTCOMES – PRIMARY. For each primary outcome, extract:

Variable	Description
Outcome measured	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Outcome definition	How outcome was defined and measured
Measurement tool/method	Instrument, scale, or method used
Time point(s)	When measured (baseline, follow-up time points)
Results - Intervention group	
N analyzed	Number of participants analyzed for this outcome
Baseline value	Mean (SD) or N (%) at baseline
Follow-up value	Mean (SD) or N (%) at follow-up
Change from baseline	Mean change (SD) or % change
Results - Control group	
N analyzed	Number analyzed
Baseline value	Mean (SD) or N (%)
Follow-up value	Mean (SD) or N (%)
Change from baseline	Mean change (SD) or % change
Comparative results	
Effect estimate	Mean difference, odds ratio, relative risk, hazard ratio (specify with 95% CI)
P-value	Statistical significance
Clinical significance	Authors' interpretation of clinical meaningfulness

Specific Primary Outcomes:

1. **Incidence of UTIs**
 - Measurement: Number of new UTI episodes per patient, incidence rate
 - Definition used by study
 - Results as above
2. **Recurrence rate of UTIs**
 - Measurement: Number of recurrent infections per year or per patient
 - Definition of recurrent UTI used
 - Results as above
3. **Time to diagnosis**
 - Measurement: Hours or days from symptom onset to diagnosis
 - Results as above

4. **Time to treatment initiation**
 - Measurement: Hours or days from symptom onset or diagnosis to treatment start
 - Results as above
5. **Healthcare utilization - Primary care visits**
 - Number of visits per patient or visit rate
 - Results as above
6. **Healthcare utilization - Hospital visits/admissions**
 - Number of ED visits, hospital admissions
 - Results as above
7. **Healthcare utilization - Teleconsultations**
 - Number of teleconsultations
 - Results as above
8. **Re-hospitalization**
 - Number and rate of UTI-related readmissions
 - Time to readmission
 - Results as above
9. **Mortality**
 - UTI-related deaths: N (%)
 - All-cause mortality: N (%)
 - Results as above

SECTION G: OUTCOMES - SECONDARY/ADDITIONAL

Same extraction template as primary outcomes for each secondary outcome measured:

1. Patient adherence to preventive measures
2. Antibiotic prescribing patterns and appropriateness
3. Adherence to clinical guidelines
4. Healthcare professional decision-making efficiency
5. Patient satisfaction and engagement
6. Quality of care indicators
7. Pathogen distribution and antimicrobial resistance patterns
8. Cost-effectiveness
9. Technology usability and acceptability
10. Implementation barriers and facilitators
11. Safety outcomes

SECTION H: TECHNOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION

Variable	Description/Notes
Integration Method	
How technology was implemented	<input type="checkbox"/> Integrated into existing EHR <input type="checkbox"/> Standalone application accessed separately <input type="checkbox"/> Workflow redesign required <input type="checkbox"/> Embedded in clinical pathway <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ____

Implementation strategy	Describe strategy used (pilot phase, phased rollout, full implementation)
Implementation duration	Time from technology introduction to full implementation
Barriers	
Technical barriers	<input type="checkbox"/> Software bugs <input type="checkbox"/> Integration issues <input type="checkbox"/> Poor internet connectivity <input type="checkbox"/> Device compatibility <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ____
Organizational barriers	<input type="checkbox"/> Resistance to change <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of leadership support <input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient resources <input type="checkbox"/> Competing priorities <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ____
Professional barriers	<input type="checkbox"/> Lack of training <input type="checkbox"/> Time constraints <input type="checkbox"/> Alert fatigue <input type="checkbox"/> Distrust of technology <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ____
Patient barriers	<input type="checkbox"/> Digital literacy <input type="checkbox"/> Access to technology <input type="checkbox"/> Language barriers <input type="checkbox"/> Privacy concerns <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ____
Facilitators	
Enabling factors	List factors that facilitated implementation (organizational support, champion presence, user-friendly design, etc.)
Professional Training	
Training provided	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Training format	<input type="checkbox"/> In-person <input type="checkbox"/> Online <input type="checkbox"/> Hybrid <input type="checkbox"/> Written materials only
Training duration	Hours of training provided
Training content	Topics covered
Ongoing support	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No; Type: _____
Feedback from Users	
Feedback collected	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Feedback method	<input type="checkbox"/> Surveys <input type="checkbox"/> Interviews <input type="checkbox"/> Focus groups <input type="checkbox"/> Usage analytics <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____
Patient feedback	Summarize key themes from patient feedback (positive, negative, suggestions)
Professional feedback	Summarize key themes from healthcare professional feedback
Usability scores	Report formal usability assessment scores (e.g., System Usability Scale) if available
Acceptability	Report acceptability ratings if available
Sustainability	
Continued use after study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
Plans for sustainability	Describe if reported

SECTION I: STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Variable	Description/Notes
Analysis approach	
Primary analysis method	Describe statistical methods used for primary outcomes
Intention-to-treat analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not reported
Per-protocol analysis	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
Handling of missing data	Method used (complete case, imputation, etc.)
Sample size	
Sample size calculation performed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not reported
Target sample size	Planned N
Actual sample size achieved	Final N analyzed
Power achieved	If reported
Adjustment for confounders	
Confounders adjusted for	List variables adjusted for in multivariable analyses

Method of adjustment	Multivariable regression, propensity score matching, etc.
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SECTION J: ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Variable	Description/Notes
Key findings	
Authors' main conclusions	Summary of authors' stated main findings
Limitations	
Study limitations	As reported by authors or identified by reviewers
Generalizability	
External validity concerns	Factors affecting generalizability of findings
Other notes	
Reviewer comments	Any additional relevant information or concerns
Contact with authors	
Authors contacted	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Information requested	Specify what was requested
Response received	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Pending
Additional data obtained	Describe

5.3 Risk of Bias Assessment in Individual Studies

5.3.1 Quality Assessment Tools

Studies will be assessed for risk of bias using appropriate tools based on study design. Two independent reviewers will conduct all quality assessments. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or third-party adjudication.

For Randomized Controlled Trials:

- **Tool:** Cochrane Risk of Bias tool version 2 (RoB 2)
- **Reference:** (Sterne et al., 2019)
- **Domains assessed:**
 1. Bias arising from the randomization process
 2. Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
 3. Bias due to missing outcome data
 4. Bias in measurement of the outcome
 5. Bias in selection of the reported result
- **Judgment:** Low risk, Some concerns, High risk for each domain and overall

For Non-Randomized Studies (cohort, case-control, before-after):

- **Tool:** Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Tools
- **Reference:** (Hilton 2024)
- **Specific JBI checklists** will be used for:
 - Cohort studies (JBI Checklist for Cohort Studies)
 - Case-control studies (JBI Checklist for Case Control Studies)
 - Quasi-experimental studies (JBI Checklist for Quasi-Experimental Studies)
 - Cross-sectional studies (JBI Checklist for Analytical Cross Sectional Studies)

For Implementation/Feasibility Studies:

- **Tool:** Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) if mixed methods
- **Reference:** (Hong et al., 2018)

5.3.2 Quality Assessment Process

- Assessment will be done independently by two reviewers using standardized forms
- Reviewers will receive training on tool application
- Disagreements will be documented and resolved through discussion
- A third reviewer will arbitrate if consensus cannot be reached
- Results will be presented in tables and summarized narratively
- Risk of bias graphs/figures will be generated using ROBVIS (Risk-of-Bias Visualization tool), RevMan (McGuinness et al., 2021), or an equivalent software.

5.3.3 Use of Quality Assessment

- Studies will NOT be excluded based solely on quality assessment
- Quality will be considered in:
 - Interpretation of results
 - Sensitivity analyses
 - Strength of evidence ratings (GRADE approach)
 - Narrative synthesis discussions
- Studies at high risk of bias across multiple domains may be excluded from meta-analysis (if performed) but retained in narrative synthesis

5.4 Strategy for Data Synthesis**5.4.1 Overview**

Data synthesis will follow a multi-step approach:

1. Descriptive analysis of all included studies
2. Narrative synthesis organized by technology type and outcomes
3. Quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) if appropriate
4. Subgroup and sensitivity analyses
5. Assessment of certainty of evidence

5.4.2 Descriptive Analysis

For all included studies, descriptive statistics will be calculated and reported to summarize study characteristics and key variables.

Categorical variables (e.g., study design, technology type, setting) will be summarized using:

- Absolute frequencies (N)
- Relative frequencies (%)
- Results will be presented in tables and visualized using figures (e.g., bar charts).

Continuous variables (e.g., participants' age, sample size, intervention duration), when reported across studies, will be summarized using:

- Mean and standard deviation (SD), when appropriate
- Median and interquartile range (IQR), when data are skewed or incompletely reported
- Minimum and maximum values (range), when available

These results will be presented primarily in summary tables and forest plots.

Descriptive summaries will also be used to report the distribution of studies according to key characteristics, including:

- Number of studies by year of publication (temporal trends)
- Number of studies by country/region (geographic distribution)
- Number of studies by study design
- Number of studies by technology type
- Number of studies by menopause stage
- Number of studies by outcome measured
- Sample size distribution across studies

Where appropriate, these distributions will be illustrated using graphical representations such as bar charts or timeline plots.

5.4.3 Narrative Synthesis

Narrative synthesis will be structured according to the Guidance on the Conduct of Narrative Synthesis in Systematic Reviews (Popay et al., 2006).

Organization:

1. **By technology type:** CDSS, telemedicine, mobile apps, AI-based tools, other
2. **By outcome domain:** Clinical outcomes, process outcomes, patient-reported outcomes, implementation outcomes
3. **By menopause stage:** Perimenopausal, menopausal, postmenopausal

Synthesis elements:

- Preliminary synthesis: Tabulation of study characteristics and results

- Exploration of relationships: Between study characteristics and outcomes
- Assessment of robustness: Quality of evidence, consistency of findings

5.4.4 Quantitative Synthesis (Meta-Analysis)

A quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) will be conducted when sufficient data are available and studies are considered sufficiently comparable.

Meta-analysis will be performed if:

- At least three studies report the same outcome.
- Studies are considered sufficiently homogeneous with respect to:
 - **Population** (menopausal women)
 - **Intervention** (same or comparable type of digital technology)
 - **Outcome** (same definition and measurement)
 - **Study design** (similar methodological design or comparable level of evidence)

If these criteria are not met, results will be synthesized narratively.

Statistical Methods

For **dichotomous outcomes** (e.g., presence of recurrent UTI):

- Effect sizes will be expressed as *Risk Ratios* or *Odds Ratios* with *95% confidence intervals*.

For **continuous outcomes** (e.g., duration of antibiotic therapy):

- *Mean Difference* will be used when outcomes are measured using the same scale.
- *Standardized Mean Difference* will be used when different scales are applied across studies.

For **time-to-event outcomes** (e.g., time to recurrence of UTI):

- Effect sizes will be summarized using *Hazard Ratios* with *95% confidence intervals*, when available.

Meta-analysis model: A *random-effects model* will be used to account for potential clinical and methodological variability between studies. A *fixed-effect model* may be considered when studies are highly homogeneous.

Presentation: Results of the meta-analysis will be presented using:

- *Forest plots* to display pooled effect estimates and confidence intervals

Summary tables reporting pooled estimates, confidence intervals, and heterogeneity statistics.

5.4.5 Assessment of Heterogeneity

Statistical heterogeneity across studies will be assessed using:

- **Cochran's Q test** (Cochran, 1954)
- **I² statistic** (Higgins and Thompson, 2002)

Interpretation of Heterogeneity

The magnitude of heterogeneity will be interpreted according to conventional thresholds (Higgins et al., 2003):

- **0–25%:** low heterogeneity
- **25–50%:** moderate heterogeneity
- **50–75%:** substantial heterogeneity
- **>75%:** considerable heterogeneity

Potential sources of heterogeneity will be explored through subgroup analyses where appropriate.

5.4.6 Stratification and Subgroup Analyses

Subgroup analyses will be conducted when sufficient data are available to explore potential differences in outcomes across relevant study characteristics.

5.4.6.1 Stratification by Menopause Stage

Objective: Examine differences in outcomes across menopausal stages

Subgroups:

- Perimenopausal women
- Early postmenopausal women (<5 years since menopause)
- Late postmenopausal women (≥5 years since menopause)

Outcomes of interest:

- UTI incidence and recurrence rates
- Effectiveness of preventive measures
- Antibiotic therapy patterns
- Utilization of non-antibiotic alternative therapies

Statistical methods

For each menopausal stage subgroup:

- *Binary outcomes* (e.g., incidence or recurrence of UTI) will be summarized using *Risk Ratios* or *Odds Ratios* with 95% confidence intervals.
- *Continuous outcomes* (e.g., duration of antibiotic therapy) will be summarized using *Mean Differences* or *Standardized Mean Differences* depending on measurement scales.

Separate *random-effects meta-analyses* will be conducted within each menopausal stage. Differences between subgroups will be evaluated using *tests for subgroup differences* implemented within the meta-analysis framework.

5.4.6.2 Comparison of Technology Users vs. Non-Users

Objective: To compare clinical outcomes between women using *digital technologies for UTI prevention* and those receiving *standard care or not using such technologies*.

Statistical Methods

For *Categorical outcomes*:

- Effect measures will include *Risk Ratios* or *Odds Ratios* with 95% confidence intervals.
- Effect sizes will be pooled using *random-effects meta-analysis*.

For *Continuous outcomes* (e.g., duration of antibiotic therapy in days):

- *Mean Difference* will be used when outcomes are measured on the same scale.
- *Standardized Mean Difference* will be used when studies use different measurement scales.

Where applicable, pooled estimates will be calculated separately for *technology users* and *non-users*, allowing comparison of effect estimates across groups.

5.4.6.3 Subgroup Analyses in Meta-Analysis

If a sufficient number of studies is available (generally ≥ 10 per analysis where possible), subgroup analyses will be conducted to explore potential sources of heterogeneity according to the following variables:

1. Menopause stage
 - Perimenopausal vs. postmenopausal
 - Early vs. late postmenopausal
2. Technology type
 - CDSS vs. other technologies
 - AI-based vs. non-AI-based tools
 - Patient-facing vs. clinician-facing tools
3. Type of UTI
 - Uncomplicated cystitis vs. complicated UTI

- First episode vs. recurrent UTI
- CAUTI vs. community-acquired UTI
- 4. Pathogen and resistance
 - MDR vs. non-MDR organisms
 - Specific resistance patterns (ESBL, CRE, etc.)
- 5. Study design
 - RCTs vs. observational studies
 - Prospective vs. retrospective
- 6. Setting
 - Community/primary care vs. hospital
 - Single center vs. multicenter
- 7. Geographic region
 - North America, Europe, Asia, other
 - High-income vs. low/middle-income countries
- 8. Comparator type
 - Active control vs. usual care

Statistical test for subgroup differences

Differences between subgroups will be assessed using the *Cochran's Q test* for subgroup differences (also referred to as the between-subgroup heterogeneity test), which evaluates whether pooled effect estimates differ significantly across subgroups.

A p-value < 0.05 will be considered indicative of statistically significant differences between subgroups.

Subgroup analyses will be interpreted cautiously, as they are considered exploratory analyses and may be subject to reduced statistical power and multiple testing issues.

5.4.7 Meta-Regression

If ten or more studies (≥ 10) are available for a given outcome, meta-regression analyses will be conducted to explore potential sources of between-study heterogeneity.

Covariates to explore

Potential moderators to be examined include:

- Menopause stage (perimenopausal vs. postmenopausal; early vs. late postmenopausal)
- Technology type (CDSS, mobile applications, telemedicine platforms, AI-based tools, other digital technologies)
- Study design (randomized controlled trials vs. observational studies)
- Geographic region (North America, Europe, Asia, other regions)

- Clinical setting (community/primary care vs. hospital setting)
- Type of UTI (first episode vs. recurrent UTI; uncomplicated vs. complicated infection)
- Sample size
- Year of publication

Method

Meta-regression will be conducted using random-effects meta-regression models to assess the relationship between study-level covariates and effect size estimates.

Both univariable and, when feasible, multivariable meta-regression analyses will be performed. Regression coefficients, 95% confidence intervals, and p-values will be reported.

Results will be interpreted cautiously due to the observational nature of meta-regression.

Software

Meta-regression analyses will be conducted using statistical software such as R (packages *meta* or *metafor*), depending on data compatibility and availability.

5.4.8 Sensitivity Analyses

Sensitivity analyses will assess robustness of findings:

Sensitivity analyses will be conducted to assess the robustness and stability of the pooled results.

The following analyses are planned:

1. *Exclusion of high risk-of-bias studies*
The meta-analysis will be repeated excluding studies classified as having a high risk of bias.
2. *Study design restriction*
Analyses will be restricted to randomized controlled trials (RCTs) only, when a sufficient number of studies is available.
3. *Outcome definition variations*
Studies using substantially different definitions or measurements of outcomes will be excluded to evaluate their influence on pooled estimates.
4. *Influential studies*
Leave-one-out analyses will be conducted to identify studies exerting disproportionate influence on the pooled effect estimate.

5. *Model comparison*
Results obtained using the random-effects model will be compared with those obtained using a fixed-effect model.
6. *Publication year restriction*
Analyses may be restricted to studies published within the last decade to evaluate the influence of more recent evidence.
7. *Sample size restriction*
Small studies (e.g., $N < 50$ participants) may be excluded to assess the potential impact of small-study effects.

Results of sensitivity analyses will be reported and discussed in relation to the primary meta-analysis findings.

5.5 Meta-Bias Assessment

5.5.1 Publication Bias

Publication bias will be assessed *when at least ten studies (≥ 10) are included in a meta-analysis*, as recommended in methodological guidelines.

Assessment methods

1. *Visual inspection: Funnel plots* will be generated to visually assess symmetry in the distribution of effect sizes relative to study precision. Asymmetry may indicate potential publication bias or other small-study effects.
2. *Statistical tests*: Formal statistical tests for funnel plot asymmetry will be conducted, including: *Egger's regression test* (Egger et al., 1997) and *Begg's rank correlation test* (Begg and Mazumdar, 1994)
3. *Trim-and-fill method*: The *trim-and-fill method* will be applied to estimate the potential impact of missing studies due to publication bias.

This method:

- Estimates the number of potentially missing studies
- Adjusts the pooled effect estimate accordingly

Interpretation

If publication bias is detected:

- Results will be interpreted with caution
- Adjusted pooled estimates will be reported
- The potential impact of publication bias on the conclusions will be discussed

5.5.2 Selective Outcome Reporting Bias

Selective outcome reporting will be assessed by comparing reported outcomes with those specified in study protocols or trial registrations, when available.

Assessment

The following procedures will be applied:

- Comparison of outcomes reported in trial registries with those reported in the final publications
- Identification of discrepancies between registered protocols and published outcomes
- Contacting study authors, when feasible, to request clarification or unpublished outcome data

Reporting

The review will report:

- The proportion of studies with potential selective outcome reporting
- The nature of discrepancies identified
- The potential impact of selective reporting on the overall synthesis

5.5.3 Other Biases

Additional potential sources of bias will be considered, including:

- Funding bias (industry-sponsored vs. independent studies)
- Conflicts of interest reported by study authors
- Early termination of trials
- Deviations from intended interventions

These aspects will be documented during risk-of-bias assessment and considered in the interpretation of findings.

6. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND FUNDING

6.1 Ethical Approval

- Not required: This is a systematic review of published literature; no human subjects research
- Adherence to ethical principles of:
 - Accurate reporting of findings
 - Transparent methodology
 - Acknowledgment of limitations
 - Proper citation of sources

6.2 Conflicts of Interest

- All team members will complete conflict of interest declarations
- No industry funding from manufacturers of digital health technologies for UTI management
- Any potential conflicts will be disclosed in publications
- Conflicts will not disqualify participation but will be transparently reported

6.3 Funding

- Funding source: [To be determined/specified]
- Funding role: Funder will have no role in:
 - Study design
 - Data collection, analysis, interpretation
 - Manuscript preparation
 - Publication decisions

6.4 Data Sharing

- Completed data extraction forms (de-identified at study level) will be made available as supplementary materials or in public repositories (e.g., Open Science Framework)
- Search strategies fully documented in appendices
- Protocol registered in PROSPERO (CRD420251052764)
- Adherence to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

7. Keywords

Primary Keywords:

Digital Health Technologies; Menopausal Women; Urinary Tract Infections; Clinical Decision Support; Prevention.

Additional Keywords:

Perimenopause; Postmenopause; Genitourinary Syndrome of Menopause; Recurrent UTI; Telemedicine; Mobile Applications; Artificial Intelligence; Machine Learning; Antibiotic Stewardship; Clinical Guidelines; CDSS; eHealth; mHealth; Evidence-Based Medicine; Implementation Science.

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